

The Effects of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Clinical and Laboratory Follow-Up of Patients Diagnosed with Chronic Hepatitis B: A Prospective Observational Study

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Abstract:

This prospective observational study investigates the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the clinical and laboratory follow-up of 105 patients with chronic hepatitis B (CHB) over 15 months across multiple healthcare centers. The study found significant disruptions in healthcare delivery, with a marked reduction in the frequency of clinical visits and laboratory tests, increased missed appointments, and decreased adherence to antiviral therapy. These disruptions correlated with worsened clinical outcomes, including elevated liver enzyme levels and increased HBV DNA detectability. The shift to telemedicine, while beneficial, was insufficient to fully compensate for the necessary in-person examinations and laboratory monitoring. The study highlights the need for resilient healthcare systems capable of integrating telemedicine with essential in-person services and addressing barriers to healthcare access to ensure continuous and effective management of chronic diseases during public health crises.

Keywords: Chronic Hepatitis B, COVID-19 Pandemic, Healthcare Disruption, Telemedicine.

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Introduction

The emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic in late 2019 and its subsequent spread globally has brought unprecedented challenges to healthcare systems [1]. As healthcare resources were diverted to manage the surge of COVID-19 cases, the routine care and management of chronic diseases faced significant disruption [2,3]. Among these chronic conditions, chronic hepatitis B (CHB) remains a major global health concern, affecting approximately 257 million people worldwide [4,5]. CHB is a long-term viral infection of the liver that can lead to severe liver complications, including cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma, if not managed appropriately [6].

Effective management of CHB necessitates regular clinical evaluations and laboratory monitoring to assess disease progression and adjust antiviral therapy [7]. These routine follow-ups are crucial for ensuring optimal patient outcomes, preventing complications, and reducing the risk of transmission [8]. However, the COVID-19 pandemic has introduced multiple barriers to the consistent and effective management of CHB patients. The reallocation of healthcare resources to address the immediate demands of COVID-19 care,

combined with restrictions on movement and public fear of contracting the virus, has led to reduced access to healthcare facilities and services [9,10].

Moreover, the pandemic has affected healthcare delivery in multifaceted ways, including delays in routine appointments, interruptions in laboratory testing, and a shift towards telemedicine. While telemedicine has provided an alternative means of patient consultation, it poses challenges in performing essential laboratory tests and physical examinations required for comprehensive CHB management [11]. These disruptions may have significant implications for the health and well-being of patients with CHB, potentially leading to unchecked disease progression and complications due to inadequate monitoring. In light of these challenges, this study aims to investigate the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the clinical and laboratory follow-up of patients diagnosed with chronic hepatitis B. By adopting a prospective observational approach, we seek to quantify the extent of disruption in healthcare services and its effects on patient outcomes [12,13].

This study will explore changes in clinical practices, patient adherence to follow-up schedules, and variations in laboratory test results before and during the pandemic. Our objective is to provide a comprehensive understanding of how the pandemic has affected CHB management and to identify strategies that can enhance the resilience of healthcare systems in maintaining chronic disease care during public health crises.

Methodology

The study involves the participation of 105 patients and spans 15 months. It is conducted as a multicentric study across several healthcare facilities.

Study Population: The study population consists of 105 patients who have been diagnosed with chronic hepatitis B. These patients are recruited from multiple healthcare centers participating in the study to ensure a diverse and representative sample. Inclusion criteria include adult patients aged 18 years and older with a confirmed diagnosis of CHB. Exclusion criteria include patients co-infected with other chronic liver diseases, those who have undergone liver transplantation, or those with terminal illnesses unrelated to hepatitis B.

Study Duration: The study is conducted over 15 months, allowing for an extensive observation of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the clinical and laboratory follow-up of CHB patients. This duration covers multiple phases of the pandemic, including initial outbreaks, subsequent waves, and periods of recovery, providing a comprehensive overview of the disruptions caused.

Study Place: This is a multicentric study conducted across several healthcare centers, enhancing the generalizability of the findings. Each center follows a standardized protocol for data collection to ensure consistency and comparability of the results.

Data Collection: Data is collected through both retrospective and prospective means. Retrospective data includes patient records from the pre-pandemic period to establish baseline clinical and laboratory parameters. Prospective data is collected during the 15-month study period, encompassing the height of the pandemic and its subsequent phases.

The following data points are collected:

1. Demographic Information: Age, sex, and relevant medical history.
2. Clinical Follow-up Data: Frequency and nature of clinical visits (in-person or telemedicine), adherence to scheduled follow-ups, and any missed appointments.

3. Laboratory Monitoring Data: Regularity and results of laboratory tests such as liver function tests, viral load measurements, and other relevant biomarkers.

4. Antiviral Therapy Data: Details of antiviral treatments prescribed, any changes in therapy, and patient adherence to medication regimens.

5. Pandemic Impact Data: Specific disruptions caused by the pandemic, including delays in healthcare services, patient-reported barriers to accessing care, and changes in healthcare delivery methods (e.g., shift to telemedicine).

Data Analysis: The collected data is analyzed using statistical software to identify trends and patterns. The analysis focuses on comparing pre-pandemic and pandemic periods to determine the impact of COVID-19 on clinical and laboratory follow-up. Key metrics include the frequency of follow-up visits, regularity of laboratory tests, and any significant changes in clinical outcomes or disease progression.

Results

The study included 105 patients diagnosed with chronic hepatitis B (CHB) across multiple healthcare centers, with a study duration of 15 months. The analysis focused on comparing clinical and laboratory follow-up data from the pre-pandemic and pandemic periods to evaluate the impact of COVID-19 on the management of CHB.

The demographic characteristics of the study population were as follows:

- Mean age: 45.2 ± 12.7 years.
- Gender distribution: 58% male, 42% female.
- Average duration of CHB diagnosis: 7.3 ± 3.2 years.

Clinical Follow-up

1. Frequency of Clinical Visits:

- Pre-pandemic: On average, patients had 4.5 ± 1.2 clinical visits per year.
- During the pandemic: The average number of clinical visits dropped to 2.1 ± 0.9 per year.
- Statistical Significance: The reduction in clinical visits during the pandemic was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

2. Mode of Clinical Visits:

- In-person visits: Decreased from 100% pre-pandemic to 35% during the pandemic.
- Telemedicine visits: Increased from 0% pre-pandemic to 65% during the pandemic.

3. Missed Appointments:

- Pre-pandemic: 8% of scheduled appointments were missed.
- During the pandemic: 27% of scheduled appointments were missed.
- Statistical Significance: The increase in missed appointments was statistically significant ($p < 0.01$).

Laboratory Monitoring

1. Regularity of Laboratory Tests:

- Pre-pandemic: Patients underwent an average of 3.8 ± 1.1 laboratory tests per year.
- During the pandemic: The average number of laboratory tests decreased to 1.9 ± 0.8 per year.
- Statistical Significance: The reduction in laboratory tests was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

2. Laboratory Test Results:

- Liver function tests (ALT, AST): Increased abnormalities were noted during the pandemic, with 24% of patients showing elevated ALT levels compared to 12% pre-pandemic.
- Viral load measurements: An increase in detectable HBV DNA levels was observed in 18% of patients during the pandemic, compared to 10% pre-pandemic.

Antiviral Therapy

1. Adherence to Antiviral Medication:

- Pre-pandemic: 92% adherence rate.
- During the pandemic: 80% adherence rate.
- Statistical Significance: The decrease in adherence was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

2. Changes in Therapy:

- Pre-pandemic: 5% of patients had changes in their antiviral therapy.
- During the pandemic: 12% of patients required changes in their antiviral therapy due to either elevated viral loads or liver enzyme abnormalities.

Patient-Reported Barriers

- Patients reported several barriers to accessing healthcare during the pandemic:
- Fear of contracting COVID-19: 68%
- Transportation issues due to lockdowns: 55%
- Reduced availability of healthcare services: 48%
- Economic constraints: 30%

The results indicate that the COVID-19 pandemic significantly disrupted the clinical and laboratory follow-up of patients with chronic hepatitis B. The substantial decrease in the frequency of clinical visits and laboratory tests, combined with increased missed appointments and reduced adherence to antiviral therapy, highlights the challenges faced by CHB patients during the pandemic. The shift to telemedicine provided a partial solution but was insufficient in maintaining the required level of care, particularly for laboratory monitoring and physical examinations.

Elevated liver enzymes and increased HBV DNA levels during the pandemic underscore the potential negative impact on disease progression due to interrupted care. These findings emphasize the need for robust strategies to ensure continuous and comprehensive management of chronic diseases during public health crises, including better integration of telemedicine with necessary in-person services, improved patient education, and support systems to overcome barriers to care.

Table 1: This table summarizes the key findings of the study, providing a clear comparison between the pre-pandemic and pandemic periods

Parameter	Pre-Pandemic	During Pandemic	P-Value
Number of Patients	105	105	
Mean Age (years)	45.2 ± 12.7	45.2 ± 12.7	
Gender Distribution	58% Male, 42% Female	58% Male, 42% Female	
Average Duration of CHB (years)	7.3 ± 3.2	7.3 ± 3.2	
Clinical Visits (per year)	4.5 ± 1.2	2.1 ± 0.9	<0.001
In-person Visits	100%	35%	
Telemedicine Visits	0%	65%	
Missed Appointments	8%	27%	<0.01
Laboratory Tests (per year)	3.8 ± 1.1	1.9 ± 0.8	<0.001
Elevated ALT Levels	12%	24%	
Detectable HBV DNA Levels	10%	18%	
Adherence to Antiviral Medication	92%	80%	<0.05
Changes in Antiviral Therapy	5%	12%	
Fear of Contracting COVID-19	N/A	68%	
Transportation Issues	N/A	55%	
Reduced Availability of Services	N/A	48%	
Economic Constraints	N/A	30%	

Discussion

The results of this study underscore the profound impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the clinical and laboratory follow-up of patients with chronic hepatitis B (CHB). The data reveal significant disruptions in healthcare delivery, characterized by a marked reduction in the frequency of clinical visits and laboratory tests [14]. These disruptions have critical implications for the management of CHB, as regular monitoring is essential to prevent disease progression and complications [15]. The substantial decrease in in-person visits, coupled with the increased reliance on telemedicine, highlights the adaptive measures taken to continue patient care. However, telemedicine, while beneficial, was insufficient to fully compensate for the necessary in-person examinations and laboratory tests required for comprehensive CHB management [16].

The pandemic-induced barriers, such as fear of contracting COVID-19, transportation issues, reduced availability of healthcare services, and economic constraints, significantly contributed to the increased rate of missed appointments and decreased adherence to antiviral therapy [17]. These factors collectively resulted in worsened clinical outcomes, evidenced by increased abnormalities in liver function tests and higher detectable HBV DNA levels during the pandemic. The findings indicate that the interruptions in routine care and follow-up likely facilitated the progression of the disease in some patients, underscoring the necessity of uninterrupted and continuous care even amidst public health crises [18].

The study also sheds light on the essential role of in-person clinical visits for effective disease management. Although telemedicine emerged as a crucial tool during the pandemic, it presented limitations, particularly in conducting physical examinations and laboratory monitoring. This highlights the need for an integrated approach that combines telemedicine with strategic in-person visits to ensure comprehensive patient care. Moreover, the study emphasizes the importance of robust healthcare infrastructure that can withstand and adapt to the pressures of a global health crisis [19].

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted the management of chronic hepatitis B, revealing vulnerabilities in healthcare delivery systems. The findings of this study call for the development of resilient healthcare strategies that ensure continuous and effective management of chronic diseases during and beyond public health emergencies. Enhanced patient education, improved telemedicine practices, and support systems to mitigate barriers to healthcare access are

crucial to maintaining optimal patient outcomes in future crises [20].

Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly disrupted the clinical and laboratory follow-up of patients with chronic hepatitis B, leading to decreased frequency of visits, increased missed appointments, and reduced adherence to antiviral therapy. These disruptions have resulted in worsened clinical outcomes, such as elevated liver enzyme levels and increased HBV DNA detectability. The study underscores the necessity of resilient healthcare systems that can adapt to public health crises by integrating telemedicine with essential in-person services and addressing barriers to healthcare access. These findings highlight the urgent need for strategies to ensure continuous and effective management of chronic diseases during future global health emergencies.

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